

Improving Unfolding Success Rate through Cloth Pose Correction

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Abstract. Cloth unfolding is a prerequisite action for most cloth manipulation tasks. Its importance has led to the development of a benchmark and a competition of cloth unfolding through re-grasping in the air, which took place at the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA). While the competition took place on a common dual-arm robot configuration, recreating it with different robot arms to develop and test algorithms has led to hardware-specific issues and solutions. In this paper, we present our implementation of the dual-arm configuration based on the one used in the competition. We also demonstrate how even a relatively rudimentary exploitation of the robot’s capability to move has led to a substantial increase in the number of possible grasps.

Keywords: robot cloth unfolding, competition, grasping, textile

1 Introduction

Advances in robotic manipulation of deformable objects have lagged behind those for rigid objects due to the significantly more complex dynamics and configuration space, since approaches designed for rigid-object manipulation cannot be directly applied to deformable, flexible objects such as textiles [1]. Besides the changing shape, textile objects also have a tendency for self-occlusion. Therefore, addressing the challenges posed by deformability is a critical step towards the advancement of robotic fabric manipulation.

Unfolding of textiles/cloth is an essential first step for a range of subsequent handling activities, such as ironing, folding, hanging, etc. Different approaches have been applied for unfolding, including the identification of key points and geometric features such as corners, edges, etc. [2]. More recently, various learning- and neural- network-based methods have been applied [3], mostly relying on computer vision [4]. Numerous other methods, approaches and tasks have been addressed in the literature, going far beyond unfolding [5].

Fig. 1: Dual-arm unfolding cell composed of 2 Franka Robotics FR3 robots in the process of unfolding a t-shirt.

Besides manipulation, grasping of textiles has also been studied [6]. One of the identified strategies is *Regrasping in the Air*, where, as the name suggests, a new point is grasped while the textile is being held in the air with one gripper. Typically, the process begins with a crumpled garment, and the first step involves grabbing the highest (or a random) point of the garment, lifting it, and then seizing the lowest point. Despite its simplicity, *Regrasping in the Air* is highly efficient, and can lead to complete unfolding in just a few grasps [7, 8].

In the scope of IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA) 2024 Cloth Competition [9], the organizers used the *Regrasping in the Air* method to evaluate grasp pose selection for cloth unfolding. Following autonomous executions of grasping the highest point and then grasping the lowest point, the competition required the participating teams (i.e., their algorithms) to determine the optimal grasp pose for the right arm of the dual-arm configuration. The grasp was then executed and the textile was stretched in front of the camera. The success of the textile stretching was evaluated based on the surface area covered by the stretched textile in front of the camera, expressed as a percentage of the maximum surface area of the textile. The dual-arm robot cell and all the procedures, except for the actual grasp selection, were provided by the organizers, enabling the competing teams to focus solely on grasp selection.

In the competition, the hardware setup was designed to mirror the anticipated capabilities of a general-purpose home assistant robot. Two 6 degree-of-freedom (DOF) UR5e collaborative robots, spaced 90 cm apart, were used in a dual-arm configuration, equipped with wrist force-torque sensors and Robotiq 2F-85 grippers. An RGB stereo-depth camera was mounted directly behind the robots at a downward angle.

1.1 Contribution

While the setup was designed to be easily reproducible, actual reproducibility is often dependent on the available hardware. In our setup, we used two 7-DOF Franka Robotics FR3 robots with joint torque sensors and mounted Franka Robotics Franka Hand grippers [10]. Besides the difference in the number of joints, leading to task redundancy, there is additionally a considerable difference in the workspaces of the two robot mechanisms. In this paper, we present our implementation with the FR3 robots, and how rudimentary robot motion helped increase grasp capabilities.

The paper is structured as follows. In the next section, we present more details on the dual-arm cell used for cloth unfolding. Section 3 presents the added motion for grasp solutions, and section 4 presents the experimental evaluation. Discussion and conclusion follow.

2 Cloth Unfolding Cell

2.1 Task

The task of the competition was to determine a grasping pose on a hanging piece of textile such that, when grasped and the textile stretched, the textile would cover the maximum surface area in front of the camera. Prior to determining the grasp pose, the textile was always picked up using the same procedure – the randomly placed textile was first grasped by the highest point and lifted. Once it settled, the lowest hanging point was grasped and lifted again.

2.2 Hardware & Software

As stated in the Introduction, the composed cell is a reproduction of the ICRA 2024 Cloth Competition cell, but composed of two Franka Robotics FR3 robots with basic Franka Hand grippers, equipped with plastic fingertips. While the camera setup remained the same, the change of the robots was reflected in the implementation of the control software. The software heavily relied on the airomono extended framework from the AI and Robotics Lab at Ghent University [11] including their cloth competition framework.

To implement a grasp motion, the depth camera provided the point cloud, which was processed and then visualized using Rerun [12], a multimodal data stack for modeling and viewing robotics-style data. A sample collected point-cloud is shown in Fig. 2-left. The image was processed with CeDiRNet-6DoF, which builds upon the point detection capabilities of CeDiRNet [13], a Center Direction Regression Network trained on the competition data to predict the grasp pose, and extends it to predict full 6-DoF grasp poses in Euler angles. Full framework description is beyond the scope of this paper. The output consisted of the ranked positions and orientations of the target grasps. In theory, moving the gripper to the determined pose should provide a good grasp for unfolding of the handled textile. Drake [14], a collection of tools for analyzing the dynamics

of robots and building control systems for them, was then used to simulate the environment with the robots and the textile. A visualization in Drake is shown in Fig. 2-right. To move from the current robot pose to the grasping pose, the task-space position was converted to joint coordinates using analytical inverse kinematics [15].

The main difference from the competition cell lies in the implementation of inverse kinematics to determine the target joint positions. FR3 robots have seven DOF, while only six are needed to completely define the position of the end-effector, resulting in task redundancy. Thus, practically infinite solutions exist for each grasp. A solution based on the geometry-based analytical inverse kinematics solver for Franka Emika Panda [15] was used, with the last wrist joint as the redundant parameter. The set of possible solutions, obtained by iterating through the possible last joint values with a step size of $\frac{\pi}{20}$, was post-processed to produce a viable joint target solution. Motion planning, using The Open Motion Planning Library [16] and Drake’s collision checking, was integrated to provide a viable, collision-free path from the starting to the target posture. The robots, table, a mesh created from the detected textile, virtual walls and virtual bounding boxes provide collision constraints. While different planners with varying results can be used, e.g. see [17], we used RRT-Connect [18], an efficient randomized algorithm for solving single-query path planning problems in high-dimensional configuration spaces. The planned path, as the output of planning, was then converted to a trajectory with Time Optimal Path Parameterization based on Reachability Analysis [19] and executed using RobotBlockSet [20], a collection of tools for robot control.

Fig. 2: Left: point cloud from the depth camera and a bounding box marking one of the grasping areas. Right: visualization of the cell with a mesh for textile, virtual walls around the robots, and ellipsoids marking the areas to where the robots tries to plan the grasping motion.

3 Changing Pose for Cloth Grasping

Besides different kinematic structure, the UR5e and FR3 robots also have very different workspaces. While the FR3 can reach 855 mm, and the UR5e similarly 850 mm, the joint limit constraints are quite different. Table 1 provides their joint limits. As shown, the range of joint motion on the UR5e robot is greater in

Table 1: Joint limit values for UR5e and FR3 robots.

robot / axis	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
UR5e max / °	360	360	360	360	360	360	
UR5e min / °	-360	-360	-360	-360	-360	-360	
FR3 max / °	157	102	166	-9	161	259	173
FR3 min / °	-157	-102	-166	-174	-161	31	-173

every joint. This has resulted in one of the major obstacles in the implementation of the dual-arm unfolding cell, as the determined target grasp would often be unreachable with the robot.

To address this, we implemented a very rudimentary error-handling procedure. If the grasp-detection algorithm, the CeDiRNet-6DoF, provided a grasp pose that is unreachable with the robot, we moved the hanging textile and re-determined the grasp pose. By executing a slow move, the textile hardly deformed. The first attempt was with the hanging position 10 cm from the center-point between the robots, marked with a blue ellipsoid in Fig. 2-right. If no collision-free solution was found, the second attempt moved the position of the hanging textile 20 cm towards the grasping robot. Finally, if even that failed, the robot moved 10 cm from the initial hanging position in the other direction. Magenta ellipsoids mark the auxiliary textile positions.

This heuristic approach solves some issues with the grasp pose being too far or too close to the robot. Figure 3 shows the three poses prior to grasping. The coordinate systems on the textile mark the determined grasp pose.

(a) Initial cloth position. (b) Cloth position near. (c) Cloth position far.

Fig. 3: Robot postures in the initial, near and far cloth positions.

4 Experimental Evaluation

To experimentally evaluate if the heuristic robot motion approach had any effect, we performed a series of experiments. Using the same initial protocol, where the robot first picks up the textile by grasping it at its highest point, and then at its lowest hanging point, we picked up 16 items. For each item, we repeated the pick-up procedure 5 times, and for each pick-up, we tested 5 variations of our algorithm to determine the grasp pose that should result in maximal surface coverage of the stretched textile in front of the camera (always at the same position). These variations involved combinations of background randomization, image cropping, joint segmentation, and the integration of RGB-D data. Thus, we performed 400 attempts at grasping textile to unfold it. Table 2 provides the results.

We can see that simple heuristic exploitation of robot motion provided a significant increase in motion. While the accuracy of the grasp-determining pose is beyond the scope of this paper, our algorithm, in our setup, resulted in a comparable average coverage to that obtained by the setup at the ICRA competition using the same grasp-determining algorithm. Figure 4 shows the results of a number of grasp attempts. Note that unsuccessful grasps are also among them.

Table 2: Grasp attempts and increase in attempt rate.

All possible grasps	400 / 100%
All attempted grasps	328 / 82.00%
Attempted without re-positioning cloth	299 / 74.75%
Increase in attempt rate	29 / 7.25 pp

5 Discussion & Conclusion

In this paper, we presented our dual-arm robot configuration that attempts to mimic the ICRA 2024 cloth competition setup. Particular focus was given on the robotic hardware and software aspects of the setup, while grasp-determining pose was beyond the scope of this paper.

We based our setup on the software framework provided by the competition organizers. Their initial framework offered an excellent starting solution, alleviating many challenges associated with the robot tasks in the competition. As discussed in this paper, the differences between our setup and the competition cell introduced new considerations regarding kinematic solutions and reachability. Our proposed heuristic approach has performed well, improving the ratio of potential grasping solutions by 7.25 percentage points.

Other than simple heuristics, a feedback system could be implemented, where the robot would, in a slow manner that does not disturb the textile, move randomly and evaluate potential reachability by re-planning. In this case, the rate of re-planning represents a bottleneck that slows down the rate. Additionally, we could use kinematic metrics, such as manipulability of the grasping robot,

Fig. 4: Various results of cloth unfolding.

to optimize the position of the textile. Both these approaches rely on knowing where the grasp pose was selected and tracking it, as determining the grasp pose in a new position of the textile is rather slow and takes several seconds. Thus, it is difficult to close the feedback loop and control the manner in which the textile is moved. As such, our heuristics approach, despite its simplicity, has proven rather successful.

The results show that exploitation of the moving abilities of the robots can be used to, in a sense, overcome joint limitations and reachability issues. In the future we will implement a feedback loop to move the the textile in a controlled manner and even more reduce the reachability constraints of the robots.

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